

Title

Self-reported vocal symptoms and acoustic voice parameters in teachers: a systematic review and meta-analysis

Review question

What is the association between self-reported vocal symptoms and acoustic voice parameters in school teachers?

Participants

School teachers (primary, secondary, or higher education)

Exposure

Self-reported vocal symptoms or risk of dysphonia measured by validated instruments (e.g., Voice Handicap Index – VHI, Escala de Sintomas Vocais – ESV)

Comparator

Teachers without vocal symptoms or with lower risk scores

Outcomes**Primary outcome:**

- Association between self-reported vocal symptoms and acoustic voice parameters

Secondary outcomes:

- Acoustic measures (jitter, shimmer, fundamental frequency, HNR)
- Prevalence of vocal symptoms in teachers
- Occupational and psychosocial factors
- Diagnostic performance of VHI vs ESV

Study designs

Observational studies:

- Cross-sectional
- Case-control
- Cohort studies

Databases

- PubMed/MEDLINE
- Scopus
- Web of Science
- LILACS
- SciELO

Search strategy

Structured search using MeSH/DeCS and keywords.

Example (PubMed):

("Teachers"[Mesh] OR teacher* OR "school teacher*")

AND

("Voice Disorders"[Mesh] OR dysphonia OR hoarseness OR "vocal symptoms")

AND

("Acoustic Analysis" OR jitter OR shimmer OR "fundamental frequency" OR HNR)

AND

("Voice Handicap Index" OR VHI OR ESV)

Search will be adapted for each database.

Data extraction

Two independent reviewers will extract:

- study design
- sample characteristics
- vocal instruments
- acoustic parameters
- outcomes

Disagreements resolved by a third reviewer.

Risk of bias

- Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (cohort/case-control)
- JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist (cross-sectional)

Data synthesis

Meta-analysis will be performed when appropriate using random-effects model (DerSimonian–Laird).

Effect measures:

- Odds Ratio (OR)
- Mean Difference (MD)
- Standardized Mean Difference (SMD)

Heterogeneity assessed using I^2 statistic.

Subgroup analysis

- gender
- teaching level
- duration of teaching career
- vocal workload

Sensitivity analysis

Exclusion of studies with high risk of bias.

Publication bias

Funnel plot and Egger's test.

Certainty of evidence

GRADE approach:

- high
- moderate
- low
- very low

Software

RevMan 5.4 and R (metafor package)